

Sarcasm Detection in Telugu Language Text Using Deep Learning

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Abstract

Sarcasm detection is a growing field in Natural Language Processing (NLP). Sarcasm is identified by using positive or more positive words, often with a negative connotation, to insult or mock others. In sentiment analysis, detecting sarcasm in the text has become critical. We have reviewed numerous relevant research articles, but due to the Telugu language's limited resources, detecting sarcasm in Telugu texts remains challenging. As a result, the sentiment detection model struggles to accurately identify the exact sentiment of a sarcastic statement, necessitating the development of an automated sarcasm detection system. Many researchers have trained and tested various machine-learning classification algorithms to identify sarcasm, but these algorithms require a dataset as their input, which often contains noise. Various pre-processing techniques are used to remove noise from the dataset. We created a Telugu News Headline dataset on our own and stored in our local machine. Labeled the statements as sarcastic or non-sarcastic by the annotators, and then input them into our proposed model. We built the proposed model using One Hot Encoding (OHE), to transform the dataset into vectors, then fed to the Sarcasm Detection Model to determine the model accuracy. We trained and tested the Sarcasm detection model on positive or even more positive sentences. Resulted accuracy with One Hot Encoding 90.30%. We observed that One Hot Encoding (OHE) had better accuracy on the balanced Telugu news headline dataset. In the future, we can apply more verticle datasets using deep learning algorithms to detect sarcasm for better accuracy.

Index terms: Natural Language Processing; Sarcasm Detection; Deep Learning; Low-resource language; RNN

Introduction

NLP lies in between Artificial intelligence (AI), computer science, and linguistics. NLP encompasses sentiment, and sarcasm is a component of this sentiment. Sarcasm, a form of sentiment, originates from the Greek term "sarkasmós," meaning "tear flesh" or "grind the teeth." Simply put, Sarcasm refers to the act of speaking with bitterness. Understanding Sarcasm is a challenge for young children, individuals with autism spectrum disorders, and some patients with brain damage. There are three types of sarcasm: verbal, gestural, and textual. Sarcasm always conveys a negative opinion, even when it employs positive or even more positive words within the text. Sentiment analysis models can't detect the exact sentiment of the given text in the Telugu language due to the underlying sarcasm in the text. A small number of researchers are currently investigating the detection of sarcasm in Telugu texts. The researchers [1] used a knowledge-based approach. This paper investigates the relevant literature, then expounds on the general architecture of the Sarcasm Detection Model and makes a distinction between different machine learning classification algorithms called SVM, NB, and LR.

Related Work

This section provides an overview of current techniques used for detecting sarcasm. The majority of research on sarcasm detection has focused on the English language. Research on low-resource languages like Hindi, Telugu, Tamil, Chinese, Arabic, and others remains limited. The study [2]–[8] discusses preprocessing, feature extraction methods, and comparing several machine learning models on a dataset of

1.3 million social media comments, including both sarcastic and non-sarcastic comments. This study [9] aims to conduct a systematic literature review (SLR) to categorise and analyse the identification of sarcasm in textual data. The hybrid Model [10] surpasses advanced techniques by 3.8%, with 80.64% SARC precision and 95.7% news headline precision. The Reference [11] hybrid model excels at 95.7% news headlines and 80.64% SARC datasets. The article [12] introduces self-training for tweet-level stress detection (SMTSD) as a new semi-supervised method that analyses four Twitter datasets and identifies those with labelled data shortages. The paper [13] explores how the integration of sentiment, emotion, and personality features using deep learning techniques can significantly enhance the performance of sarcasm detection in social media content, particularly on tweets. The paper [14] explores different methodologies for analysing political text areas. The paper [15] investigates how education uses sentiment analysis, or opinion mining, and considers how NLP can evaluate student feedback and improve instruction. The abusive comment detection model [16] performed well. The study [17] categorizes Hindi sentiment analysis approaches and discusses their effects on SA issues, levels of analysis, and performance evaluation. The paper [18] provides a decision tree classification method for Twitter emoticons. The deep learning architecture [19] improves sarcasm detection using the COMET model and textual data. Sarcasm identification in computational linguistics [20] is expanding using rule-based, statistical, and deep-learning methods. This study [21] found hyperbole in an unbiased dataset, which improves sarcasm recognition. This study [22] uses the Abu Farah and Misogyny datasets to detect Arabic sarcasm and misogyny. This study [23] offers a new multi-stage deep learning architecture (MSDLA) for Tamil language sentiment analysis. The paper [24] contains Mann Ki Baat transcription and concludes that a fully effective MLP system requires many tools and strategies to improve language processing accuracy and efficiency. The paper [25] discusses irony and sarcasm detection in Italian. The researchers compare five deep learning systems and find that the top one achieves a 93% F1-Score. The Chinese translation model AlexNet achieves better semantic recognition accuracy than other neural network algorithms [26]. Popular choices of classification algorithms include Naïve Bayes, support vector machines (SVM), hidden Markov models (HMM), gradient-boosting trees, and random forests [27]. Researchers and developers have used machine-learning approaches to detect toxicity [28–30]. The paper [31] presents a hybrid CNN-LSTM model for sentiment analysis on social media data, achieving 91.3% accuracy. The paper [32] proposes a model for extracting product features and sentiment from online reviews using word segmentation, LSTM neural networks, and the LDA topic model. The model proposed in [33] outperforms traditional methods in accurately analysing sentiments from qualitative data. The study in [34] reveals that factors such as age, English language nativeness, and country have a significant impact on the perception of Sarcasm. These findings suggest that incorporating sociocultural variables can improve the design of social analysis tools to better understand and detect Sarcasm online. The paper [35] highlights improvements in preprocessing, segmentation, and POS tagging to enhance the corpus's reliability and usefulness. The paper [36] presents a novel approach called EmoTrans, which uses the transitions between different emotions within a text to detect sarcasm. References [37–38] suggest a model for POS tagging that is based on machine learning and deep learning. They also create a dataset that has been manually annotated and look into deep learning architectures like RNNs. These models deal with the linguistic complexity of low-resource languages and achieve higher accuracy and robustness, making NLP capabilities for low-resource languages much better.

Proposed Methodology

Introduction: We build the proposed methodology with the One Hot Encoding, Positional Encoding and with Word2Vec techniques.

Dataset Collection: In this paper, we have created our own Telugu language News Headline sarcasm dataset, which includes 943 Telugu Headlines. We applied it to kappa coefficient statistics. The Telugu language is the most widely spoken in India. For detecting sarcasm in Telugu-language text, there is only a limited dataset available in online repositories like Kaggle. The proposed methodology architecture describes how the modules will execute the input given to them, and it contains modules as depicted in Figure 1. The proposed system contains modules like preprocessing, vectorisation, model creation, and model evaluation.

Figure 1: Architecture of the Proposed Methodology

Source: Made by authors

Architecture: Architecture describes how the modules will execute the input given to the model and system modules are depicted in the figure 1.

Annotation: Telugu language experts received the collected datasets and manually labeled the sentences to determine whether they were sarcastic or not.

Pre-processing: Pre-Processing The initial stage in pre-processing is to convert text documents into a readable word format. The papers possess numerous characteristics that prepare them for the next stage of text categorization. The process parses a document into a list of tokens after treating it as a string. Removing stop words: Since stop words are frequently used, we must eliminate unimportant terms. In data preprocessing, we remove punctuation. Data preprocessing may contain other punctuation, but in our dataset, we only have limited punctuation, such as commas, full stops, exclamatory marks, open brackets, and closing brackets. Preprocessing is a crucial module in any language or text. The goal of preprocessing is to eliminate any noise from the corpus. Bag of Words techniques convert textual data into vectors of numbers, enabling machine learning classification algorithms to perform tasks such as classification, semantic analysis, and prediction.

Vectorization: The process of converting data into numbers is called vectorization. The machine cannot understand words, so it requires numerical values to make it easier for it to process the data. To apply any type of algorithm to the data, we need to convert categorical data into numbers. We convert the preprocessed data into vectors through vectorisation. During the classification phase to evaluate and interpret natural language data, such as text or speech, NLP requires the integration of deep learning techniques. The most common evaluation metrics include accuracy, precision, recall, and f1-score. The Telugu language is the most widely spoken in India. For detecting sarcasm in the Telugu language, there are limited datasets available on online repositories.

Model building and Evaluation: Finally the model is build with deep learning recurrent neural network and evaluated using neural network dense layers internally as shown in Fig 1. In the Recurrent Neural Network the data cycles through the loop and the output is determined by the current input and previously received input. The middle consists of multiple hidden layers, each with its activation functions, weights, and biases. These parameters are standardized across the hidden layer so that instead of creating multiple hidden layers, it will create one and loop it over.

Table 1. Web Based Translated Sentences

English Sentence	Transliteration	Translation in Telugu	Dataset Type
Rulers who are taking development back in their countries like a time machine	Tama desalalo abhivrddhini taim meshin laga venakki tisukeltunna palakulu	తమ దేశాలలో అభివృద్ధిని సైంమెషిన్ లాగ వెనక్కి తీసుకెళ్తున్న పాలకులు	Sarcastic
Osmania University has a hundred years of history	Osmania university vanda endla charitra kaladi	ఉస్మానియా యూనివర్సిటీ వంద ఏండ్ల చరిత్ర కలది	Non-Sarcastic

We used a web-based translator to translate the English-language dataset into Telugu. It is a statistical translation system. Existing translation systems are effective at some level, but some words in a sentence do not translate according to context, as shown in Table 1. In this context, we need post-processing, as shown in Table 2. Preprocessing is a crucial module in any language or text-processing application. In this paper, we used preprocessing to remove noise from the corpus. It includes eliminating special characters and removing unwanted text using the Escaped Unicode Representation.

Table 2. Post Processing for telugu language text

Telugu Sentence	Escaped Unicode Representation	Post Processing	Dataset Type
“మీ సలహాలు మేము పాటించలేనంత గొప్పగా ఉన్నాయ్”.	“మీ సలహాలు మేము పాటించలేనంత గొప్పగా ఉన్నాయ్”.	మీ సలహాలు మేము పాటించలేనంత గొప్పగా ఉన్నాయ్	Sarcastic
“చెక్కతో చేసిన ఉపగ్రహాన్ని ప్రయోగించనున్న జపాన్”.	“చెక్కతో చేసిన ఉపగ్రహాన్ని ప్రయోగించనున్న జపాన్”.	చెక్కతో చేసిన ఉపగ్రహాన్ని ప్రయోగించనున్న జపాన్	Non Sarcastic

Computers are symbolic processing machines. Computers process numbers quickly, but they cannot understand any text data. All machine learning and deep learning algorithms work with numbers very efficiently. We cannot process text directly with algorithms, and we need an encoding system for translating text data to numerical vectors. Vectorization is the process of converting text data into numerical vectors. In this paper, we tested deep learning recurrent neural network for the Telugu language sarcastic and non-sarcastic datasets. We divide our dataset into training and testing segments using varying ratios. In the following section, we provide a detailed analysis of the results.

Result & Analysis

We collected a sarcastic and non sarcastic telugu news headline dataset from the different online opensource platforms like news websites, comedy shows, printed telug news papers .The collected dataset was imbalance because sarcastic sentences were 1580 and non-sarcastic sentences were 842. We used the oversampling method to balance the dataset, resulting in 842 sarcastic sentences and 842 non-sarcastic sentences. We conducted experiments on the balanced dataset using the Python environment and accounted for the data distribution, also known as training and testing measures. We use the One Hot Encoding to determine the accuracy of the model.

Fig 2: One Hot Encoding Confusion Matrix for balanced Telugu News Headline dataset

Figure 2 shows the balanced Telugu news headline dataset confusion matrix. There are 198 true negatives, 0 false negatives, 38 false positives, and 183 true positives. We used standard sigmoid activation function which is applied final dense layer of the neural network. It is calculated using the following mathematical formula. This activation function is used in binary classification tasks that is sarcastic and non sarcastic where sarcastic is represented as 1 and non sarcastic is represented as 0 (zero). The output of the model lies in between positive class and negative class. Positive class is labelled as 0 (zero) and negative class is labelled as 1.

Table 3. Result of the RNN on balanced Non Sarcastic and sarcastic telugu news headline dataset

Model	Dataset type	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy
One Hot Encoding	Non Sarcastic	1.00	0.83	0.91	90.30%
	Sarcastic	0.84	1.00	0.91	

Table 3 shows the result of one hot encoding with recurrent neural network on telugu news headline dataset. Using python environment the dataset is trained and tested and after we tokenized to find the word index and applied appropriate padding and used sigmoid activation function to create the rnn model and finally compile the model with adam optimizer. Precision in non sarcastic was 1.00 little higher than sarcastic which is 0.84, Recall in non sarcastic was 0.83 little lower than sarcastic which is 1.00 and F1-score was equal in sarcastic and non sarcastic but precision and recall made difference in accuracy finding in the model.

Fig 3: Result Analysis of RNN with One Hot Encoding

Figure 3 shows Precision, Recall and F1-score validation accuracy when experimented with deep learning one hot encoding technique. Thick blue color indicate non sarcastic validation accuracy and thick brown color indicate sarcastic sentence validation accuracy and X-axis indicate performance metrics called precision, recall and f1-score and Y-axis indicate validation accuracy from 0.00 to 1.20.

Conclusion

The objective of this paper is to design a Model for detecting Sarcasm in Telugu Language text. We used One-Hot Encoding word embedding Model and Deep Learning Recurrent Neural Network. We observed that the majority of researchers worked on Western languages, and few researchers are working on low-resource language called Telugu. To demonstrate the potential of our approach, we conducted experiments on Telugu News Headline dataset. We tested our vectors using Deep Learning Recurrent Neural Network with one-hot encoding and observed the performance measures precision, recall, f1-score and accuracy. We used standard sigmoid activation function which is applied final dense layer of the neural network.

We trained and tested our Model using one hot encoding word embedding method and obtained the accuracy 90.30% on the Telugu News Headline Dataset. One Hot Encoding brings a high accuracy rate. In the future, the breadth of this Model might be applied to detect Sarcasm automatically using more verticle datasets using more word embedding techniques with deep learning approaches.

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